

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL DESCRIPTIVE STUDY TO
DETERMINE THE LACTATE LEVEL SIGNIFICANCE IN THE
CEREBROSPINAL FLUID WHILE DIFFERENTIATING VIRAL
AND BACTERIAL MENINGITIS****¹Dr. Muhammad Ammar Bashir, ²Dr. Maham Sabir Rao, ³Dr Fareeha Bashir**¹Medical Officer, RHC Jamke Cheema²Sheikh Zayed Hospital Rahim Yar Khan³Allied Hospital Faisalabad**Abstract**

Objective: The research objective is to determine Cerebrospinal Fluid Lactate level's diagnostic accuracy while differentiating Viral and Bacterial Meningitis with CSF-culture as Gold-Standard.

Materials & Methods: We conducted this cross-sectional, descriptive study from January to August 2017 at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore on a total of 126 meningitis suspicion patients having ten-to-forty years age, both genders. We excluded patients having a history of immune-suppressive therapy, antibiotics intake, sub-arachnoid haemorrhage/seizures, brain trauma, tuberculosis, and recent strokes. We measured the CSF LLs in every patient. CSF LLs was the base of diagnosing BM ($LL \geq 3.80$ mmol/L) or VM ($LL < 3.80$ mmol/L) among patients. There was a correlation in CSF-culture and lactate diagnosis.

Results: The percentage of male and female patients was 58.7% (74) and 41.2% (52) among 126 (1.4:01 male-to-female ratio) patients having a mean age of 26.4 ± 8.1 years. According to CSF LLs, 64.3% (81) patients were having BM. CSF-culture provided confirmation of BM among 65.8% (83) patients. On CSF-culture, among CSF LLs positive (81) patients, we found BM and VM among 75 (TP) and 06 (FP) patients respectively. We found 08 (FN) and 27 (TN) patients with BM and VM respectively among 35 patients with CSF LLs negative. We found specificity, PPV, NPV, sensitivity, and DA with 86.0%, 92.6%, 82.2%, 90.3%, and 88.9% respectively on CSF LLs in differentiating VM and BM.

Conclusion: The study finds CSF LLs with great specificity and sensitivity in differentiating BM and VM and recommends its use in the general routine of differentiating meningitis.

Keywords: Bacterial Meningitis (BM), Viral Meningitis (VM), Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF), Lactate Level (LL), Standard Deviation (SD), True-Positive (TP), False-Positive (PF), True-Negative (TN), False-Negative (FN), Positive-Predictive Value (PPV), Negative-Predictive Value (NPV), and Diagnostic Accuracy (DA).

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Please cite this article in press Muhammad Ammar Bashir et al., A Cross-Sectional Descriptive Study To Determine The Lactate Level Significance In The Cerebrospinal Fluid While Differentiating Viral And Bacterial Meningitis., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Meningitis is the acute inflammation of protective-membranes of spinal cord and brain [1]. The causes of this inflammation are micro-organism, virus or bacteria and certain drugs [2]. Meningitis causes many morbidities and mortalities especially among paediatric population despite medical advancements in infectious diseases [3]. The difference in an age group involved in the type of bacteria causing BM. Group-B streptococci and Escherichia coli (digestive-tract bacteria) are mostly the causes of this disease among new-borns or premature babies. Listeria mono-cytogenes that occur in epidemics may affect the new-borns [4]. Streptococcus pneumonia (Serotypes-6, -9, -14, -18, and -23) and Neisseria meningitides affect older children while Haemophilus influenzae type-B affects children under 5 years in countries with no vaccination [4, 5]. Both Streptococcus pneumonia and Neisseria meningitides cause 80% of BM among adults. Fifty years above have more risk of being affected by Listeria monocytogenes [6, 7]. Pneumococcal vaccines have decreased pneumococcal meningitis among adults and children [8]. BM can cause severe complications which depend upon causal micro-organism as well as geographical region and status and a factor of immunization [9]. Abro AH et al. showed BM among 64% meningitis patients [10]. An abrupt and appropriate treatment of BM is essential to avoid its complications. BM is better treated with antibiotics whereas AM (Aseptic Meningitis) limits itself [11]. The differential diagnosis of BM is lengthy with many infectious/non-infectious diseases. Comorbid conditions, age, and clinical manifestation provide clues in BM diagnosis. Accurate diagnosis is possible with findings of CSF examination including culture results and Gram stain [12]. With the suspicion of BM, starting empiric therapy is necessary considering epidemiologic trends while selecting antibiotic for therapy. Causative organism determines the length and drug selection of the treatment when BM diagnosis confirms. We may find improved outcomes with the use of adjunctive corticosteroids [13]. Differentiation of BM and VM is not easy so CSF variables like glucose, proteins, serum glucose and leucocytes count combination is an effective suggestion in this regard [14]. However, diagnosis and differentiation of BM and VM come with many other limitations. CSF LL is a better suggestion parameter in differentiating BM and VM [15]. Lactate exists in the human body as stereoisomers with L and D lactate type and is a hydroxy-carboxylic acid. L-lactate contributes in the metabolic acidosis of the human body, thus is a major physical enantiomer [16]. The existence of D-Lactate is (1-

5%) of L-Lactate in a human body [17]. When anaerobic conditions are present, bacteria produce L and D-Lactate [18, 19]. This shows that bacteria have the ability to produce both L and D-Lactate while the human body can only produce L-Lactate. If bacteria produce an increased lactate level in CSF then diagnosing BM will be easier as D-Lactate would be easy to measure. Viallon A et al. finds 94% and 92% sensitivity and specificity respectively at (3.8 mmol/L) cut-off level of CSF LL while differentiating VM from BM [20]. BM leads to mortality or morbidity if not diagnosed/treated timely and accurately thus it required a highly accurate diagnostic method of BM and VM differentiation. As CSF LL is possibly helpful data in this regard, hence we conducted this study to determine the diagnostic accuracy of using CSF LLs in VM and BM differentiation in our local population. The outcome can guide us in opting this method as our routine practice for in-time diagnosis and management to reduce mortality and morbidity in our population.

Operational Definitions:

Meningitis: The presence of vomiting, fever of >100 F, Nuchal rigidity (neck-muscle tone increased and stiff), Kernig's sign positive (feeling pain while extending knee passively from ninety degree knee flex), Brudzinski's sign positive (Neck flexion leads to hip and knee flexion), and having neutrophilic pleocytosis, protein raise, and low sugar with (>10 cells/mm³), (>45 mg/dl), and (<40 mg/dl) respectively at CSF examination.

CSF Lactate levels: CSF LLs of (≥3.8 mmol/L) and (<3.8 mmol/L) taken as BM and VM respectively.

True-Positive: Patients of BM on CSF LLs having positive CSF-culture for bacteria.

True-Negative: Patients with negative CSF-culture with no BM on CSF LLs.

False-Positive: Patients having negative CSF-culture with BM on CSF LLs.

False-Negative: Patients having positive CSF-culture with no BM on CSF LLs.

DA: Having terms as:

Sensitivity = TP/Cases of CSF-culture positive x 100

Specificity = TN/ Cases of CSF-culture negative x 100

PPV = TP/ Cases of CSF-culture positive x 100

NPV = TN/ Cases of CSF-culture negative x 100

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

We conducted this cross-sectional, descriptive study from January to August 2017 at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore on a total of 126 meningitis suspicioned patients having ten-to-forty years age, both genders. We excluded patients with a history of immunosuppressive therapy, antibiotics intake,

tuberculosis, brain trauma, recent stroke, and those unwilling to be part of the study.

We selected/admitted 126 patients fulfilling inclusion criteria and after taking Local Ethical Review Committee's permission. We took informed consent, relevant history of each patient and then measured their CSF LLs (by a 3-years post-fellowship pathologist). According to operational definition, we diagnosed patients with BM or VM on their CSF LLs. We correlated this data with CSF-culture findings and recorded all data on pre-designed Proforma.

The study used SPSS for analysing data. We recorded mean and SD for quantitative variables (duration of disease, age, and CSF LLs). We also recorded the percentage and frequency for qualitative variables (BM, VM, and gender). To differentiate VM and BM, we used a 2-by-2 contingency table, calculating PPV, NPV, DA of CSF LLs, specificity and sensitivity (taking CSF-culture as Gold-Standard). Through stratification, we controlled effect modifiers (age, duration of disease, and

gender). We applied post-stratification Chi-Square taking P value as ≤ 0.05 significant.

RESULTS:

We took 126 patients with 10 to 40 years age having mean age as (26.4 ± 8.1) years. Most of the patient 38.1% (48) were of 21-30 years age-group. The ration of male and female patients was 58.7% (74) and 41.2% (52) with a male-to-female ratio of (1.4:1) respectively. We recorded (19.7 ± 9.4) hours as the mean duration of disease. We diagnosed BM among 64.3% (81) patients through the support of CSF LLs while CSF-culture confirmed 65.8% (83) and 34.1% (43) patients with BM and VM respectively. Among CSF LLs "Positive" (81) patients, the number of patients with BM and VM was 75 (TP) and 06 (FP) respectively on CSF-culture. Among CSF LLs "Negative" (35) patients, the number of patients with BM and VM was 08 (FN) and 27 (TN) respectively on CSF-culture. We found specificity, PPV, NPV, sensitivity, and DA with 86.0%, 92.6%, 82.2%, 90.3%, and 88.9% respectively on CSF LLs in differentiating VM and BM.

Table – I: Distribution of Gender and Age (126)

Age and Gender		Number	Percentage
Age	10 – 20 Years	33	26.19
	21 – 30 Years	48	38.10
	31 – 40 Years	45	35.71
	Total	126	100
Gender	Male	74	58.73
	Female	52	41.27
	Total	126	100

Table – II: Results' Summary

Outcomes Summary	Positive on CSF Lactate Levels	Negative on CSF Lactate Levels	P-Value
Positive on CSF Culture	75 (TP)	08 (FN)	0.791
Negative on CSF Culture	06 (FP)	37 (TN)	

Sensitivity: 100.0%, **Specificity:** 94.44%, **PPV:** 93.75%, **NPV:** 100.0%, **DA:** 96.97%

Table – III: NPV, PPV, Specificity, Sensitivity and Diagnostic Accuracy

Details	Percentage
Diagnostic Accuracy	88.89
NPV	82.22
PPV	92.59
Specificity	86.05
Sensitivity	90.36

Table – IV: Age, Gender and Disease Duration for Negative and Positive on CSF Lactate Levels

Details		Positive on CSF Lactate Levels	Negative on CSF Lactate Levels	P-Value
10 - 30 Years (33)	Positive on CSF Culture	15 (TP)	00 (FN)	0.805
	Negative on CSF Culture	01 (FP)	17 (TN)	
21 - 30 Years (48)	Positive on CSF Culture	31 (TP)	05 (FN)	0.646
	Negative on CSF Culture	03 (FP)	09 (TN)	
31 - 40 Years (45)	Positive on CSF Culture	29 (TP)	03 (FN)	0.818
	Negative on CSF Culture	02 (FP)	11 (TN)	
Male (74)	Positive on CSF Culture	55 (TP)	04 (FN)	0.690
	Negative on CSF Culture	02 (FP)	13 (TN)	
Female (52)	Positive on CSF Culture	20 (TP)	04 (FN)	1.000
	Negative on CSF Culture	04 (FP)	24 (TN)	
Disease Duration ≤ 24 Hours (67)	Positive on CSF Culture	38 (TP)	05 (FN)	0.858
	Negative on CSF Culture	04 (FP)	20 (TN)	
Disease Duration > 24 Hours (59)	Positive on CSF Culture	37 (TP)	03 (FN)	0.845
	Negative on CSF Culture	02 (FP)	17 (TN)	

Age stratification (10 – 30) Years (33):

Sensitivity: 86.11%, **Specificity:** 75.0%, **PPV:** 91.18%, **NPV:** 64.29%, **DA:** 83.33%

Age stratification (31 – 40) Years (45):

Sensitivity: 90.63%, **Specificity:** 84.62%, **PPV:** 93.55%, **NPV:** 78.57%, **DA:** 88.89%

Gender stratification (Male) (74):

Sensitivity: 93.22%, **Specificity:** 86.67%, **PPV:** 96.49% **NPV:** 76.47%, **DA:** 91.19%

Gender stratification (Female) (52):

Sensitivity: 83.33%, **Specificity:** 85.71%, **PPV:** 83.33%, **NPV:** 85.71%, **DA:** 84.62%

Disease's duration stratification (≤ 24 Hours) (67):

Sensitivity: 88.37%, **Specificity:** 83.33%, **PPV:** 90.48%, **NPV:** 80.0%, **DA:** 86.57%

Disease's duration stratification (> 24 Hours) (59):

Sensitivity: 92.50%, **Specificity:** 89.47%, **PPV:** 94.87% **NPV:** 85.0%, **DA:** 91.53%

DISCUSSION:

The study purpose is the determination of DA of CSF LLs in BM and VM differentiation taking CSF-culture as Gold-Standard. We diagnosed BM among 64.3% (81) patients through the support of CSF LLs while CSF-culture confirmed 65.8% (83) and 34.1% (43) patients with BM and VM respectively. Among CSF LLs "Positive" (81) patients, the number of patients with BM and VM was 75 (TP) and 06 (FP) respectively on CSF-culture. Among CSF LLs "Negative" (35) patients, the number of patients with BM and VM was 08 (FN) and 27 (TN) respectively on CSF-culture. We found specificity, PPV, NPV, sensitivity, and DA with 86.0%, 92.6%, 82.2%, 90.3%, and 88.9% respectively on CSF LLs in differentiating VM and BM. Abro AH et al. finds CSF LL in BMs cases with (14.96 ± 6.13) mmol/L having 73.40% of PPV and 98.30% of sensitivity. Gastrin B et al. finds in his study that CSF LL helps in diagnosing BM and differentiating it from VM with sensitivity and specificity of 97% and 82% respectively [21]. Genton B et al finds specificity, sensitivity, and predictive value as 100%, 95%, and

96% respectively [22]. However, Robert L et al. find no significant results of CSF LLs in differentiating VM and BM but found it effective like glucose and protein content and leukocyte count [23]. Kleine TO et al. found 100% of both specificity and sensitivity of CSF LL in differentiating BM and VM [24]. Schwarz S et al. shows this percentage to be 94 and 43 for sensitivity and specificity respectively while Viallon A et al. shows 94% and 92% sensitivity and specificity respectively at a cut-off level of (3.8 mmol/L) of CSF LLs in diagnosing BM from VM [25, 20]. Huy NT et al. finds pooled-sensitivity from (0.86-1.0) with 0.96 mean and confidence interval of 95% (0.95-0.98) while pooled-specificity had (0.43-1) with 0.94 mean and 95% (0.93-0.96) confidence interval in his meta-analysis.

CONCLUSION:

The research concludes that CSF LL is a rapid-performing and accurate diagnostic method in differentiating BM and VM with supporting in early diagnosis of bacteria. Therefore, its use in our general-practice routine is a better choice for

diagnosing BM and VM accurately to decrease mortality and morbidity among these particular patients.

REFERENCES:

1. Blazer S, Brant M, Alon U. Bacterial meningitis. Effect of antibiotic treatment on cerebrospinal fluid. *Am J Clin Pathol.* 1983; 80:386-87.
2. Agueda S, Campos T, Maia A. Prediction of bacterial meningitis based on cerebrospinal fluid pleocytosis in children. *Braz J Infect Dis.* 2013;17(4):401-4.
3. Chen Z, Wang Y, Zeng A, Chen L, Wu R, Chen B, et al. The clinical diagnostic significance of cerebrospinal fluid D-lactate for bacterial meningitis. *Clinica Chimica Acta.* 2012; 413:1512-15.
4. Ewaschuk JB, Naylor JM, Zello GA. D-lactate in human and ruminant metabolism. *J Nutr.* 2005; 135:1619-25.
5. McLellan AC, Phillips SA, Thornalley PJ. Fluorimetric assay of D-lactate. *Anal Biochem.* 1992; 206:12-6.
6. Kiechle FL, Kamela MA, Starnes RW. Lactate production by aerobic bacteria grown in cerebrospinal fluid. *Clin Chem.* 1984; 30:1875-6.
7. Tunkel AR, Hartman BJ, Kaplan SL. Practice guidelines for the management of bacterial meningitis. *Clinical Infectious Dis.* 2004;39(9):1267-84.
8. Van de Beek D, de Gans J, Tunkel AR, Wijdicks EF. Community-acquired bacterial meningitis in adults. *New Eng J Med.* 2006;354(1):44-53.
9. Hsu HE, Shutt KA, Moore MR. Effect of pneumococcal conjugate vaccine on pneumococcal meningitis. *N Engl J Med.* 2009;360(3):244-56.
10. Agrawal S, Nadel S. Acute bacterial meningitis in infants and children: epidemiology and management. *Paediatr Drugs.* 2011; 13:385-400.
11. Abro AH, Abdou AS, Ali H, Ustadi AM, Hasab AAH. Cerebrospinal fluid analysis – acute bacterial versus viral meningitis. *Pak J Med Sci.* 2008;24(5):645-50.
12. Huy NT, Thao NTH, Diep DTN, Kikuchi M, Zamora J, Hirayama K. Cerebrospinal fluid lactate concentration to distinguish bacterial from aseptic meningitis: a systemic review and meta-analysis. *Crit Care.* 2010;14(6): R240.
13. Greenlee JE. Approach to diagnosis of meningitis. *Cerebrospinal fluid evaluation. Infect Dis Clin North Am.* 1990; 4:583-98.
14. Cohn KA, Thompson AD, Shah SS, Hines EM, Lyons TW, Welsh EJ, et al. Validation of a clinical prediction rule to distinguish Lyme meningitis from aseptic meningitis. *Paediatrics.* 2012;129(1): e46-53.
15. Jaijakul S, Arias CA, Hossain M, Arduino RC, Wootton SH, Hasbun R. Toscana meningoencephalitis: a comparison to other viral central nervous system infections. *J Clin Virol.* 2012;55(3):204-8.
16. Kim KS. Acute bacterial meningitis in infants and children. *Lancet Infect Dis.* 2010; 10:32-42.
17. Sáez-Llorens X, McCracken GH. Bacterial meningitis in children. *Lancet.* 2003;361(9375):2139-48.
18. Ginsberg L. Difficult and recurrent meningitis". *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry.* 2004;75Suppl 1(90001):16-21.